

Geographical, Economic, and Socio-Political Determinants in the Development of Natural Ports: A Comprehensive Analysis

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Abstract: This paper presents an in-depth exploration of the maritime industry in Malaysia, with a specific focus on the development and implementation of natural ports as a sustainable solution to the challenges faced by the global port industry. The thesis highlights the strategic importance of the Straits of Malacca and examines the roles of Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd in advancing the Ship-to-Ship (STS) transfer method and integrated port solutions. These innovations are seen as critical to maintaining Malaysia's competitive edge in the maritime industry, particularly in comparison to Singapore's established ports. The Kuala Linggi International Ports (KLIP) is identified as a pivotal component in this strategy, offering advanced facilities for liquid bulk cargo transfer and playing a significant role in the transshipment of goods from various global regions.

The study aims to identify, analyze, understand, evaluate, and recommend how the concept of natural ports can be implemented globally, emphasizing their economic and environmental benefits. The research addresses several key factors influencing the development of natural ports, including cost, location, government regulations, customer satisfaction, competition, and marketing strategies. It also considers the broader implications of these developments on Malaysia's economy and employment rates, suggesting potential for significant contributions to the maritime sector and beyond.

Keywords: Natural Ports, Maritime Industry, Sustainability, Malaysia's Maritime Strategy, Ship-to-Ship Transfer (STS).

I. INTRODUCTION

The study represents industry of ports in Malaysia, mainly Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd which is connecting Straits of Malacca. This paper will address on the Ship-to-Ship or STS and the integrated solution port which is initiated by Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd to the shipping and port industry within ASEAN region and globally. This paper will explore the information on the variation of the ports in the world today including existing different types of ports and the glitches concerning these ports today; the hindrance and weakness to the shipping industry; and the solutions of STS and integrated port solution port which Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd to the shipping and port industry globally.

Highly competitive Singapore ports are equipped with strategies that can fulfil the global demand. This is a losing ground for Malaysia as many prolific factors must be considered before establishing foothold globally. However, Singapore is geographically in a strategic position which connects east and west which allows greater efficiency and scale of operation. The key area and great availability make Malaysia one of the favoured nations to enter the Southeast Asian market. In the course of the most recent decades Malaysia saw an amazing increment in compartment traffic through its ports, abandoning other rising economies in the locale. Since 2000 Malaysia recorded a 400% development in compartment throughput, presently taking up right around a fourth of all holders took care of in the locale. Twenty years back this was as yet 10%. This is nothing unexpected. Malaysia is directly at the core of the locale where intercontinental and intra-Asian ocean

freights meet one another. Singapore remains the main port in the district, yet has little space to extend and less associations over land. With a lot of reasonable land accessible, very much kept up foundation and a prospering economy, Malaysia will just reinforce its effectively solid situation as the doorstep of the area, and advantage from rising holder traffic in Southeast Asia. According to TheEdgeMarkets (2019), Malaysia Lack of a national strategy to coordinate the ports is one of the major reasons why Port of Tanjung Pelepas (PTP) and Port Klang continue to play bridesmaids to Singapore when it comes to transshipment containers, according to industry observers. Transshipment refers to the shipment of goods to an intermediate destination before reaching their final destinations.

The maritime industry plays a crucial role in global trade and economic development. In this context, the thesis by Noormustafa Kamal Yahya provides an in-depth exploration of Malaysia's maritime industry, focusing on the development of natural ports as a sustainable solution to the industry's challenges. This article summarizes key aspects of the thesis, highlighting the strategic importance of the Straits of Malacca, the roles of Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd, and the case study of Kuala Linggi International Ports (KLIP).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Increasing external cost in the form of pollution and congestion harming the lives in ocean, especially when there is an increase in demand for international trade pave way for busy waterway globally. According to a reference, Container ships make about 9,000 port calls, and vehicle.

Based on the research objectives, it is questionable in terms of implementation of Natural Port as the which determinant would affect process most. Building a port incur high cost, however the statement of making it profitable also supported by another factor. Having said that it is still remain unclear in terms significance of other factors for instance strategic location. Comparing with Singapore, if the statement of strategic location is true that makes the ports become more competitive naturally or are there possibilities to create an ordinary location to be strategic.

There is also issue of building a natural port, where despite this concept is exist however why not many ports are promoting globally, even though in general we can conclude it can benefit the environment via limited usage of fuel, controlled movement, as well as reduce emission into the ocean, protecting the marine biodiversity.

Port Dickson is a place where nearest and weekend beach hangout for population in the central region has been lately suffering from poor quality of water and loss of marine lives due the fact that overexploitation of Malacca Straits waterway. Port Dickson is the main seaside area in Negeri Sembilan, Malaysia which is a most loved end of the week escape for individuals from Malaysia just as Singapore. Effects of the travel industry exercises, shipping, processing plants, land recovering exercises, waterfront zone the board development and lacking sewage water treatment are the most squeezing ecological issues that have caused disintegration of water quality in Port Dickson. Consequently, remembering all the effects towards water nature of Port Dickson, water quality investigations identified with Port Dickson are quickly looked into. This is to give a general perspective of flow circumstance of water quality status, recognize and organize future examinations and administrative plans in Port Dickson. Broad Port Dickson water quality investigations were done from 1999 to 2002 up until now, Port Dickson waters have been examined as far as physico-compound parameters, supplements, natural carbon, microbiological and substantial metals to demonstrate ecological contamination. Be that as it may, restricted investigations were accessible on overwhelming metal fixation in the waterfront waters of Port Dickson. After 2002, less examinations were directed as far as water quality in Port Dickson. This survey yield indicated that water quality related investigations in Port Dickson are unmistakably should have been expanded and planned as far as research targets. Investigating contamination factors in Port Dickson, amassing of substantial metals in water, silt and bio monitors examines are urgent now of time. Future examinations on overwhelming metals are vital to comprehend effects of various natural compartments from different anthropogenic sources. Future examinations in Port Dickson ought to likewise give a concentration in usage of this asset all together fill in the information hole and give away from in practical advancement of this valuable asset. In the midst of these discoveries, genuine degree of defilement in Port Dickson will provide guidance accommodating suggestions on natural administration and contamination control right now.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The main key point of this study is about natural ports which also can be expressed as sustainable ports. The literatures also express findings based on theoretical framework, which are independent variables namely cost, location, regulations, customer satisfaction, competition, management team and marketing mix which affects development or implementation of Natural port.

1. Ports

According to Lirn (2013), the ports which work in a greener way allows improvement in terms of nature and economy which is imperative due to the fact that scarcity, finite resources but unlimited needs and wants. As the principal confirmations of natural emergency began, the agreement that, financial development can't be accomplished inconclusively with the current use design, began to emerge among the worldwide networks. It finished in UN Conference on the Human condition in 1972 as the idea of reasonable improvement. This idea proposes that it is conceivable to accomplish monetary development and industrialization without ecological harm.

Throughout the decades, the meaning of maintainable advancement developed. It is characterized as "the advancement that addresses the issues of the present without trading off the capacity of people in the future to address their own issues". This tends to two crucial issues the need of monetary development to reduce destitution and the issues of ecological debasement that go with financial development. Along these lines, this idea has three measurements: Social improvement, Economic development and Environmental insurance – that comprehensively guarantees a decent personal satisfaction to everybody. Water port activities or commonly known as maritime transport has been key driver back in history and now as it permits transfer of liquid and bulk goods from one end to other end of the world. This operation is vital as it gives opportunity to countries to contribute to the globalisation while improving economic growth.

Crude materials, for example, iron metal and unrefined petroleum are shipped in mass from their place of inception to preparing offices, for example, impact heaters or processing plants. Prepared merchandise are utilized by makers to create completed products, with creation offices frequently found away from the fundamental markets for the finished result. The final results must be moved from the production line to the business sectors. Sea transport gives both the limit (if there should arise an occurrence of iron mineral and unrefined petroleum) and a minimal effort for each unit for these vehicles. Air transport is restricted by space and weight limitations and has a lot greater expense, but with a higher speed. Land transport by truck or train may not be accessible (if there should arise an occurrence of intercontinental transports) and may likewise have a greater expense (both as far as monetary expenses and, if there should be an occurrence of truck transports, regarding ecological impression)

Marine insights cites that there are many forms of ports accessible worldwide where it is nice worldwide. The first port forms are Inland ports, constructed on comparatively limited water areas such as lakes or shore. Inland ports are ports focused on fairly limited water sources, such as streams or reservoirs. They may be for freight purposes, travelers or both. Traditionally, inland ports are established or usually held on the coastline of small conduits such as bay, stream or estuaries and drifts are often seen often. Many of these inland ports may enter the ocean with a trench system. All things considered ports are focused on inland conduits they usually carry on like traditional seaports, but they are not ready to require deep draft transport traffic. A number of inland ports may often be rendered specifically for leisure purposes requiring for limited sized boats that may only be used for sailing and fishing exercises. Inland ports, unlike the stopped seaports, are renowned for their consistency to operate smoothly. These ports may also be referred to as dry ports, which are like complex multi-purpose core points. The Montreal inland port is the largest. Inland ports are typically held here to extinguish the storage and load shipping needs, and they are often made available to travelers. These are shallower than seaports, so they don't require deep docking, but inland ports only docking is permitted. Inland vehicle administrations are used to connect these inland ports (mostly called rail or street terminals) by marine terminals. St. Lawrence Seaway is a significant inland harbor.

Multi-purpose shipping and tanker ships are at their peak in the universal sector owing to the development of inland ports additionally referred to as inland container appropriation ports, which are a center point for inland conduit exchanges primarily due to their free space connectivity blockage and ample cap. Inland terminal is the key connector to exchange efforts between two districts, inbound traffic and outbound traffic. This port will also comply with different measured activities. Significant elements of inland ports are described below as: established transport environments for freight dispersion Inland port Depots should be rendered available to ensure sufficient capability of masses and containers that can later be used on different deliveries. Calculated division will be agreed to manage all teamwork activities much like stock documents. There will be a legal logistics center to house save sections of freight and other equipment involved with payload stacking.

Angling ports are associated with the corporate community because they are engaged in angling. Angling drills may also be used as distraction process. The success of an angling port depends solely on fish accessibility in that sea area. An angling port may be an inland port. Angling ports are enticing port often used for leisure activities or feeling. Those are the ports that make their customers regulated and restricted angling. These are the largest ports earning profits while working

properly. Unlike other forms of ports, the angling port has an operating escape provision, meaning means this port works while fish are available in the port region or jurisdiction. In the region's fish scarcity, such ports are inefficient. Similarly, angling ports need more help fills as compared with other ports, such a large amount are almost shutting. There are ports of littler depth owing to the angling vessel's draft being reduced to a small distance. An angling port includes: hangers: the unique zone used to cover goods and products. This also houses production as a ability area that creates and stores essential nourishment or various items for fish. Supply post: This is a major piece of an angling port which is essential for the boat's fuel requirements which freshwater appeal. Construction of Service and Administration: which is the guiding concept under which preparations are created for the trip and angling, as well as the executives with any legitimate medical issues. Premises: The system that holds fish agreements is either fish acquisition or fish bidding.

Any ports are heated water ports, ports where water is held warmer. A warm water port's most favorable thing is that it won't freeze in harsh winters. Consequently, service is allowed during the freezing season without an ephemeral closure. Such ports establish the nation's economy. These ports play a critical role in local financial development. Two other high-income terminals are Valdez in Alaska and Vostochny in Russia. The primary explanation why warm water ports are deemed important and why substantial created world's nations fly to set up and have even warmer water ports is it allows constant exchange, given even in the cold winter, when various ports deny their regulation, warm water ports are still operative and touch importers. These warm seaports allowed inland traffic into potential nations like Ethiopia. This is the primary explanation for worldwide market growth. Any amazing models can include Ukraine's Odessa, Russia's Vostochny Port, Murmansk Port, Japan's Kushiro, and Valdez's Alaska.

Furthermore, dry ports are classified as inland terminals that can be linked via street or rail transport offices to a seaport and are usually used as multimodal management focuses. A dry port is helpful in storing and clearing exchange, and may help decrease the unavoidable clog close seaport. Its capability is near a seaport, with the main distinction not coordinated around the coastline. Used mainly for inland load transshipment. It is a seaport-affiliated trans-shipment terminal, controlling illicit activity involving paying and co-appointment between retailers and exporters. These ports play a similar function as organization's body's veins, since they are used to link merchants and exporters from distant areas who can not access seaports for trade or other purposes. India alone has 300 to 330 dry ports, and more will be worked on. A dry port includes all the required facilities as sufficient freight devices, rail sidings, storage areas and cargo yards to operate with secure shipping leeway.

Seaports seem to be the most acknowledged types of terminals used in the maritime shipping practices. These ports concentrate on an ocean area and offer accommodation for large and small vessels. Various seaports are established around the coastline, efficiently managing continuous cargo transfers. Often recognized as a load or transport point, a seaport. Maybe more existing seaports are now used for leisure purposes. Outstanding distribution centers are also equipped for shipment and routine legging. It that also have services such as lodgings, cafés, port meeting places, bathrooms and restaurants to improve the enthusiasm of people entering the port. Seaports are the world's growing and busiest terminals. The most well-known ports and important components of water transport are seaports. They are divided into three classes: Cruise Port, Call Port, and Freight Port.

Cruise Home Ports, which are kind of a terminal, invests considerable time in handling travel submit exercises and providing travelers the stage to reach and land travels separately to the start and finish of excursions. Furthermore, a home port is designed to have the necessary arrangements for a sumptuous trip. The supply can change from fuel assets to crisp drinking water, wines, foods, etc. A typical home port travel is continuously clogged, buzzing with individuals filling up or leaving travel. These are the busiest ports for continuous boarding; stacking; emptying activities. Additionally, the port authority prearranges and conducts all customs and courses of action for a safe journey by transport. Throughout South Florida, Miami ports become the world's cutting-edge transportation hub. In addition, Port Everglades and Florida and Puerto Rico's San Juan port are separately deemed notable for their intended journeys. A component of the well-known homeport travel involves Florida's Port of Miami and Port Everglades, and Port of San Juan, Puerto Rico. Call point: Also recognized as the midway point, Port of call is somewhere halfway on the boat's itinerary element to recognize fuel supply and storage or empty tank. Port of Call is a kind of port where a boat on the road pays a quick stop. It is often used to do simple repair works. Various travelers will exit the ship at a "call button." It stands in as a layover location, in a particular vessel's home ports.

Popular vessel-operated cargo terminals. As the name implies, such ports operate according to the freight it handles, and convenient facilities vary from port to port. These are excellent ports for handling freight only. Often recognized as "bulk

ports," "split bulk ports," or "boat ports." The cargo ports include several automated loading or dumping strategies. A freight port may also be equipped to handle single and more than one product type. Things such as fuels, additives, meal crops, wood, machinery and motorcars are shipped to a variety of locations using a freight port's suitability. Deep water ports are often used alongside container ports that don't have enough depth to accommodate big ships. Freight such as coal, liquid naturally occurring substances or gasoline, meal grains, vehicles, etc. are handled by bulk ports while intermodal product or freight in containers is handled by container ports. Often a 0.33 group is now included in this list, and that's all-in-one port this sort of port also not only manages special freight but can accommodate all freight types on one ship. Frequent operating terminals branch from character bulk ports and are delegated to manage different forms of ship lading. Dockworkers are the firms who serve as port managers and ride roughshod over the numerous operating ports.

Containerization requires a distinctive distribution strategy to organize. Every transfer from one transmission to another requires computer to execute the transfer. This unit is complex, weighty, and knotted to a physical site; the carriage process must be coordinated to utilize the uncommon method safely. This involves the usage of storage areas to decouple the different stages of the shipping process; loading in a container terminal is a perfect illustration of one of such storage nearby.

There are also many forms in which goods known as intermodal transport may be described as transporting goods in one and the same load unit or vehicle through various modes of transport without managing the goods themselves during transfers between modes, e.g. container transport by rail and road. The European Union and national governments have long supported it because of its eco-friendliness and raising traffic congestion. It is also used where a change in modality is needed, e.g. where transporting products from China to Germany and use rail transport from the sea port to an inland terminal.

According to study, this may raising indirect costs that are detrimental to human safety, even creating environmental danger. This may be also explained if intermodal transport faces less environmental danger. Benefits of mistreatment trains or barges instead of trucks are economies of volume (reduced price per container) and less pressure on location, though at speed costs. The ultimate journey, either from a port instrumental terminal, an inland barge instrumental terminal or a rail terminal, is by truck to carry the instrumentalities to the client. (Some customers may either be immediately adjacent to a multimodal terminal or probably have their own terminal, but this may be occasional.) Ship to Ship or best known as Floating ports is becoming increasingly common in Malaysia as it draws foreign investors to develop this strategy. Recent reports from the New Straits Times Malaysia revealed that Hutchison Ports from Hong Kong would spend nearly US\$180 million to build this STS hub program in Tanjung Pelepas, Johor, currently run by KA Petra. Another reputable report from Star News says Malaysia is expected to host the world's largest Ship-to-Ship (STS) transport centre, which can handle the berthing of 30 petroleum-based goods and liquefied natural gas (LNG) vessels.

Achieving cost leadership approach is crucial by effectively implementing economies of scale, where total manufacturing cost savings is feasible when rising output units. Ports have negotiating leverage over vendors because they can get incentives for more quality efficiency, known because purchasing ecosystems, giving them comparative edge over rivals. [Magretta, 2011]. The port now has servicing plants in several developing countries, allowing cost benefit to be built at the detriment of consumers (O'Brien, 2018). This would help the above-mentioned approach where generating low-priced resources may be successful, with greater focus on scale economics. This may be achieved simultaneously and externally. For example, bulk purchasing and management experience may benefit internally, while externally affecting facilities and job market.

In order for STS concept to stay in the aggressive environment of shipping industry, they must differentiate themselves. Innovative research and development needed to produce high quality products. Must be in line with latest technology like adapting to mobile platform such as Android which can be used in the vessel operations. This particularly not differentiating them with competitive ports like in Singapore or Hong Kong, however getting into such so might allow ports to compete in a hostile manner. This might bring the prices down as well as forces business to innovate and improve their hardware and software (Magretta, 2011)

Shipping can redefine itself by introducing more new low range gadgets to compete with Hyundai in the heavy industry. As Singapore successful competes with many local and international rivals, but yet they have high market share compare to even some competitive ports. Singapore and Hong Kong have their own high-end market and customers are extremely loyal to the brand, where they post complex buying behavior when it comes to shipping (Magretta, 2011). Superior after sales- service is important to convince the customers where they get associated with port operators for a long period of time. Loyalty creates brand value (Forbes.com)

2. Ship to ship transfer

Transfer process of ship-to-ship (STS) is the movement of cargo between maritime vessels situated side-by-side, whether anchored or afloat. Cargoes usually transported using STS techniques involve crude oil, liquefied gas (LPG or LNG), bulk freight, and petroleum. The etymology of STS conversion can be used in connection to procedures employed by commercial merchant ships when distinct from underway purification which is the word utilized by the U.S. Navy for specific, but typically much more complex, military vessel activities when underway. Most freight activities are between ships and land-based ports. However, moving freight from one carrier to another may also be helpful, so this is called ship-to-ship service as it can save time and reduce cost. One vessel should serve as the bridge, the other mooring. The receiving ship is called the daughter vessel and the shipping vessel is called STBL or Mother vessel (Fatehi & Choi 2008).

When involved the carrier dummy variable in terms of ship-to-ship transfer, the presence of vessel operation significantly decreases the price on routes, however, the market concentration and route density variables do not impact on price as much as authors expected. Vowles (2000) performed a regression model to explain the variance in water port pricing. The regression involved several variables assumed have effect on the water port pricing such as distance, resort, CMA factor, hub, low, market share of vessel and waterway and the market share of the largest carrier in the market. According to the coefficients of model results, each additional presence of vessel operation is predicted to depress the water way charges by 45.47% which implies that low-cost carriers do have a remarkable effect in pricing. However, Vowles (2000) considers that this outcome is not sufficient, because this variable does not measure the percentage of schedule of vessels and bulk cargos offered by low-cost cargos. So the CMA variable and the market share of the low-cost carriers have been added in the model to compensate the weakness. It convinced that the entry of CMA airline immediately decrease the price on the specific route by 77.61%.

Other related papers extend the research to other impacts of the entry of the low-cost cargos, such as the effect on competitors on the market the low-cost cargos joined, the impact of alternative market in the same serving region, the consumer welfare, the reaction from the established cargos in the market the low-cost cargos entered, and the geographical competition in the whole air transport industry. Although investigations about the impact of the entry of low-cost cargos have been installed in different aspects, they all get the final conclusion related to the pricing effect. That is the low-cost carriers' entrance definitely decreases the price with the increase of passenger traffic, resulting in the gain of consumer welfare.

In Malaysia, ship-to-ship transfer is getting popular, where Johor Port will be the market target spot for this service. According to Straits times Singapore , Malaysia is building a multimillion-dollar venture at Johor's Tanjung Pelepas harbour, which would allow vessels to move their commodities to several other vessels without ever being docked at the berth. The project will cover a surface area of 1,200 hectares, more than three times the size of Sentossa Island, likely to cost between US\$ 150 million (\$203 million) and US\$ 180 million. It is being built near Tuas in the Strait of Johor

Figure 1: 2.4 Theoretical framework

Above figure shows independent and dependent variables. Based on the topic of this paper, the dependent variable is implementation of the Natural Port which makes success venture. However, it might be largely affected or influenced by independent variables which are cost, location, regulations, customer's satisfaction, competition, management team and marketing mix. Cost element encompasses profitability and cost structure as well as metrics used. Location depicts geographical element of the Linggi port in the coast of Malacca. Besides that, customer satisfaction also considered as one of the independent variables which to certain extent expected to affect the port operation. In addition to that, competition also considered as an independent vector in spite TAG Marine and LBSS claiming that they will be able to differentiate themselves compare to other regional competitors. Following independent variable is the effectiveness of the management team. Top management executives; their leadership style; policy how it will affect the implementation of the Natural port as well as STS concept. Other than that, marketing mix elements also discussed as part of independent variable. Marketing mix element consists of four Ps. Product in this case service offered such as shipyard, fabrication yard, tank storage, Bunkering, Offshore mooring, platform and floating storage units on top of STS. Price the cost for clients, where the liners and tanker operators inclined to pay various fees when they use the service. In addition to that, promotion also part this variable which includes above and below the line. Above line promotion targets wide range customers for instance television and radio advertisement. While below the line promotion is about targeting specific range of customers. Some of the examples of below-the-line promotions are sponsorship, buy one get one free, free sample and sales promotions.

3. The Strategic Importance of the Straits of Malacca

The Straits of Malacca are a critical maritime passageway, linking the East and West. This strategic location positions Malaysia as a pivotal player in the global shipping industry, facilitating significant container traffic and playing a major role in regional trade.

Critical success factor of this business will be the location, which is strategic along Malacca Straits where ships will sail through to reach the main port which is in Klang. Besides, that the Kuala Linggi International Ports (KLIP) has solid business foundation which allowing strategic decision can be made as the business has been around for the since 2006, sending strong message the business is a pioneer in innovative liquid transfer process. Heavy investment in physical assets such as the shipyard possesses loadout facilities comprising an efficient 7,000-tonne capacity Synchronist shiplift system, and boasts two loadout skidways and quays. The yard also possesses approximately 540-metre length wharfage for ships. There are also high-tech equipment in the port which is valuable such onboard machines and cranes as well. However, the participation of human in this process should be addresses as it is part of the success factor. Human connects with machines and technology for better performance and meet the kpi

Figure 2: Project Contribution for better performance

4. The Role of Linggi Base Sdn Bhd and TAG Marine Sdn Bhd:

These two companies have been instrumental in advancing innovative solutions in the maritime sector, particularly in Ship-to-Ship (STS) transfer methods and integrated port solutions. Their initiatives have helped position Malaysia as a competitive force in the maritime industry, challenging the dominance of Singaporean ports.

West port Country's largest container terminal the Westports is located in Port Klang. Along the coast of straits of Malacca, this port post significant threat to Tag Marine. The port is also handling liquid cargoes, such as transfer of Gasoline, crude oil or special oil, liquified petroleum gas, and liquid chemical. According to the interviewees, the port of capable hanging containers., dry and bulk. However the question Mark's here, TAG marine is highly specialized in handling the TEUs. Most of the information collected for section are also based on references collected by the interviewees. Even though the questions are mostly open ended where it requires opinion however since under this section, the interviewees also should use factual evidences to answer that is important. Another question asked was how TAG Marine able to handle the competition. The common answer all of them was KLIP is it distinctive position to over the threat in the. The core competency of Port lies on the STS where it is efficient and reduce costs to the shipping company. Ad hoc services provided by TAG attracts more vessel operator to use service at an economic price. By differentiating themselves, Port Linggi, able to sustain in long term while developing ancillary and other ship related activities in that area One interviewee also highlighted that more port authorities can be stationed in the ports, allowing seamless operation compare to other port. The port is promoting a concept of green port to natural port. This means it attempts to reduce carbon emissions which can be harmful. Despite many ports are putting on this, however weak implementation part causing failure on top of funding for the project.

5. Kuala Linggi International Ports (KLIP): A Case Study:

KLIP, established in 2006, is a prime example of Malaysia's maritime capabilities. Its strategic location and advanced facilities for liquid bulk cargo transfer make it a key player in the transshipment of goods globally. The port's development in phases highlights the evolution of Malaysia's maritime infrastructure.

KLIP was established in 2006 located in Kuala Linggi, Melaka, Malaysia; a private port area gazetted under the laws of Malaysia. The reason of why Kuala Linggi was chosen is due to its ideal location for an industrial port for STS transfer of liquid bulk cargo due its suitable water depth. It is located in the middle of Malacca Straits which serves key waterway linking Asian and European trade where 83,740 vessels transited in 2016 and the number grows year by year. This KLIP evolves in 3 phases in which the first phase is the current existing harbour limits for offshore STS operations as explained above. The second phase of KLIP involves the reclamation of 620 acres for future enhancement plan where in its third phase, it leads to the establishment of integrated onshore facilities & solution which includes, Shipyard, Fabrication yard, Tank storage, Bunkering, Offshore mooring, platform and floating storage units , Industrial training centre, Office government departments and agencies and Premises for financial and commercial business. In essence, KLIP evolves from just an industrial and natural port that just provide STS crude and LPG transfer into a port that provided an integrated solution.

The STS and the integrated solution port are the solutions it offers to the whole shipping and ports industry which is to be explained and illustrated in detail through this defence proposal and thesis. Ships like oil tankers and gas carriers carry huge amount of cargo in bulk which does not have to be unloaded in just one port but at different ports. Even some carriers like VLCC and ULCC which are massive in size does not berth in port or jetty for discharge operation due to draught restrictions. In such condition ship to ship transfer is utilized.

6. The Development of Natural Ports: Economic and Environmental Perspectives:

The concept of natural ports, as advocated in the thesis, offers an eco-friendly approach to maritime operations. This concept aims to reduce environmental impact while maintaining economic viability. The study delves into various factors affecting natural port development, including cost, location, regulatory environment, and customer satisfaction.

A lack of literature on Natural ports from a private sectors point of view shows a gap in organisation's understanding of the causes and effects of this phenomenon. More importantly there is little research into the strategies that organization of private sector to enhance port operation Additionally, the literature indicates that covers the independent variable which are cost, regulations on ports, strategic location, satisfaction of customers, rivalry among ports (if any), effectiveness of management team, as well as utilization of marketing mix where are number of consequences, thus further research that

explores strategies and its consequences of retention is necessary. Employees' contribution in achieving STS as a sustainable port is crucial.

According to Crouch (2013), today executive level employees are more attracted to new challenges and responsibilities. Therefore, by only investing in the improvement and training might result in the risk of losing those workers due to other job opportunities in the market. Rodriguez (2008) stated that training and development can be an important retention enhancing strategy, as long as the employee feels that they are growing, however, if they feel that they are no longer growing, training and development alone will not serve the purpose of retaining (Hong et al, 2012) the employees who will be part of the management team to achieve the excellence.

IV. INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Total of five important samples were collected via qualitative research interview and secondary sources using internet, reference books, prospectus and other related researches. The general finding of the company shows the inception and intention where it requires in-depth understanding of the port operation conducted by TAG Marine. The company is mainly focusing in transferring LNG and LPG done through ship-to-ship (STS) approach. Based on the profile questions, since the history of the company is status quo, the most important aspect is time of inception and ranking of management team. According to the interviewees the company was formed in the year of 2000 in the month of March and the founder/chairman would be YBhg Datuk Wira Noormustafa Kamal Bin Yahya. Further information collected from them shows other individuals in the management teams are executive director Ybgh Datuk Capt. Mohd Zanif Hashim, Marine advisor Ym Raja Datuk Malik Saripulazan, Chief Executive Officer Ybgh Dato' Muhammad Saifullah Noor, Deputy CEO, YBHG Dato' Muhammad Saifullah Noor, Director of Marine Project, Commander Ramli Bin Johari (Rtd) And Head Of Marine Operations Captain Shamsul Kamal Ibrahim. In terms of descriptive analysis, interviewees age range is between 45 to 55 years old with minimum qualification of degree in maritime and business. None revealed, the income earned hence no data on this.

The study is specifically interpretative because it attempts at understanding a functional process (Lin 1998), perhaps even the channel governance process. Furthermore, the multi-case architecture helps one to find certain similarities through instances, and therefore often incorporates a far more positivistic perspective into to the analysis. Although this study uses the singular case based on TAG Marine and KLIP, the networks it's not a study as described either through Eisenhardt (1989), Stake (1994) or Yin (1994). This is not a situation-study, as the research does not go across each network's comprehensive scope and historical perspective.

In this study there is no specific explanations of every channel contextually. And, as it was demonstrate next, the sources of information of evidence are interviews which are accompanied by findings and records in terms of secondary research. However, those above references are secondary in significance. This thesis is therefore a quantitative interview review of four network control events: a comprehensive examination of 4 events 76 utilizing interviews and rooted analysis of hypothesis form (Creswell 1998; Marshall and Rossman 1995 Miles and Huberman 1995).

Data compilation the primary records are excerpts from the in-depth, voice-recording interviews with members of each network's coordinating team. It was triangulation of these techniques of data collection with other sources of evidence observation and documentation (Huxham 2002; Marshall and Rossman 1995) to shed light from various viewpoints and experiences (Fine, Weiss, Wessen and Wong 2000). In this research, both source triangulation were used, with respect to interviewees, and method triangulation, between interviews and other data (Janesick 2000; Miller and Crabtree 1994; Richardson 2000). The sampling of data sources involves settings, events, and people (Marshall and Rossman 1995; Miles and Huberman 1994 see below for justification of source sampling)

Interviewee sampling the interviewees were selected with a theoretically driven within-case sampling strategy, allowing for enough flexibility to account for the rolling quality of such within-case sampling (Miles and Huberman 1994). Initially, the design included four sets of interviews per case: one individual and three group interviews. Representatives from the network's coordinating unit (the network manager and other staff) and from member organizations were interviewed. In total, 5 interviewees were conducted. They are Managing Director, Chief Executive Officer, Marine Advisor, Head and Director of Marine Operations and Projects. Interviews were conducted individually as the respondents are unaware of the feedback given by each other. It is critical in decision as it can prevent biasness among audience hence quality decision can be made based on frequency of similar type of opinion given.

The table below illustrates demographic distribution of the samples. Based on the interview which was conducted via phone call or face-to-face, three questions were asked. These are age range, qualification, and income information. There is one respondent within the age range of 30-40 and another one 1 respondent is above age 60. Majority of the target audience are in the category of 41-50 which means mostly they are well experienced individual in the shipping field. Next demographic variable is about qualification. 2 respondents hold degree as their basic qualification while 2 participants have Masters qualification. There is one sample from the population with professional qualification, perhaps something about shipping and liner industry. The final question was about their income range. All of them were cooperative as they are unreluctantly shared this sensitive information. One respondent admitted that his salary range is between RM10,000 to RM20,000. There are two respondents fall under the income range of RM20,001 and RM30,000 while 2 more individuals are earning more than RM30,001. Income range more or less can give idea of hierarchy order in the organization. All respondents are male as there are no females in the senior executive position. This can be a limitation of the study as the view of female leaders can be different in certain context which might increase the value of this research.

Table 1. Demographic finding

	Demographic		
Age	30-40	41-50	51-60
	1	3	1
Highest qualification	Degree	Master	Professional Qualification
	2	2	1
Income (per month)	10, 000-20, 000	20, 001-30, 000	30, 001 and more
	1	2	2

1. Cost and profit

The question asked was “How the company is making profit? What are the metrics used?”. Most of the interviewees were willing to disclose about revenue stream of the port where it is mainly coming from STS service charge. Besides that, the company also providing floating storage service to the clients. According to one of the interviewees, the floating charges for oil and gas crude oil carrier pays lucrative revenue to TAG Marine. On top of the distribution and break bulking and blending. Large tankers and other vessel use this service. Another interviewee emphasized on the cost of operation which is mainly wages and salaries, supplies, utilities, interest on loan and other variable and fixed costs. The emphasis given on capital expenditure as well, where the cost of machines and other support transportation to assist the operation.

Interviewees also revealed that, marine cost charged by the firm competitive compare to other national and regional ports which can benefit the liners. The revenue also derived from as pilotage, berthing and tug assistance during dry docking. Dry docking service as per one of the interviewees will be a plan which will be added in the future once the port is built as a one stop centre. This also allows strait of Malacca to be more attractive with more add value services. KLIP will be part of the success of the plan as more vessels calls allow more services can be offered if other ports in the same coast are focusing on container service.

One interviewee highlighted about metrics used in the cost structure. Main metrics used are financial ratios such as profitability ratios shows return to business based on revenue or sales generated in a given period of time. Liquidity ratios also part of the metric which can be used to benchmark against industry average. It is paramount to determine how healthy the company is in achieving the target in terms of finance. Cashflow relates to liquidity that reflects earned cash, sales, and loan capital. It implies the movement of money to and from the business that requires a stable continuous flow of money that is necessary for short-term operation of the company. For example, paying vendors, wages, utilities and other day-to-day expenses.

Another question asked under this vector is “How the costs are being managed?”. Most of the interviewees credited the excellence of finance department in managing the expenses and controlling the budget. Budgetary control is a system of

strategies placed to ensure that the real profits of an organization are sticking close to its cash-related arrangement. The system usually involves identifying key targets for financial personals based on the expenditure cap, along with a lot of compensation enabled when the goals are met. (Interviewee 2 &3)

Often, expenditure plan and actual statements are regularly given to those in the budget summaries with a responsibility to detail; they are then anticipated to make a step to fix any adverse variations. As per Cliché, (2012) Budgetary control system compares salaries and uses and the structured compensation and usage with the objective which reflects efficiency in terms of planning, co-ordination, motivation and control.

2. Location

Under this category of the first question asked was about “share brief history about the location and the port”. Based on the information collected from the interviewees, there are similarities among all in terms of answers where the location is primarily situated outside of the shipping traffic. This is located at the mid-way in the straights of Malacca. The respondents are claiming that the port is not competing with any surrounding ports such as Sungai Udang port which operated by Petronas to transfer hydrocarbon, and petroleum related products, more than 300,000 dwt. Another port which is not directly competing with KLIP will be Tanjung Bruas where it handles dry-bulk and liquid-bulk as well as general cargos, allowing outer and inner berth of vessels. According to the respondents the port is servicing barges, which are A barge is a shoal-draft flat-bottomed boat, built mainly for river and canal transport of bulk goods. Originally barges were towed by draft horses on an adjacent towpath. It also provide service to supply and service vessels. There reason why it is not competing with KLIP, it is about the water level which shallower with 8.5m depth at outer berth and 5 meters depth with tidal restriction at inner berth of vessels.

All interviewees were clear about the history of the location. History says Malacca's strategic position, again, according to interviewees. The marine kingdom of Srivijaya, centered on Palembang, Sumatra, came to power in the 7th century, and its presence spread to the Malay archipelago. The dynasty established absolute control of two significant Southeast Asian territorial entry points which are the Malacca Strait and the Sunda Strait. By initiating a sequence of wars of conquest and strikes on possible competitor ports on both sides of the strait, Srivijaya consolidated its economic and diplomatic supremacy in the region, which lasted for approximately 700 years. The Kingdom of Srivijaya benefited greatly from the profitable trade in spices, e.g. the vassal trading network with China, and trade with Arab and Indian traders. Representatives of the study are well informed of the past of the site and of the Malacca Strait, where they stated that it was an significant maritime trading route between India and China. The emergence of the Malacca Sultanate in the 15th century, the Johor Sultanate and the emergence of the modern urban state of Singapore have made it a major factor in international trading networks.

Under different historical times, many large regional powers dominated the straits. The Dutch and UK governments created an imaginary divide in the northern region in the early 19th century, agreed to hunt down and destroy pirates on their respective sides, forming the new boundary between Malaysia and Indonesia, safe from foreign attacks. The history of strategic location teaches us the position of Malacca now, imperative to justify why KLIP is situated to support the vessels. To date, in 2016 there were 83, 740 vessels transit and discharge happened as it is waterway which connects east and the west. The Very Large Crude Carrier or simply VLCC are tankers which pass by the straight experiencing increase of 20%, one of the reasons why KLIP is position in a strategic location (Suhaila, 2013).

More information from the interviewees prove that KLIP is positioned in the area where it is in mid-way in the Straits of Malacca, with further increase in year on year traffic in terms of vessel operation. Main advantage is about it provides of convenient and safety to use service provided in KLIP. The location is not only strategic in terms on sea, but also inland network. The link to north-south highway is just 15 minutes away with the distance of 25km, while airport KLIA can be reached within 1.5 hours with the distance of 110km. the focus will be land transport from KLIP as it is cost effective and more efficient adding to value to the clients. The location is also equipped with efficient traffic separation scheme which supports the operation. There is also inshore Traffic zone within this location.

The following question was : What are the significances of the port? The inshore traffic zone is unregulated and is not intended to be used for through traffic but rather for local traffic, fishing and small craft. A ship navigating in a traffic-lane should sail in the general direction of that lane. The body of water between two opposite lanes is to be avoided by vessels travelling within the TSS as far as possible except in certain circumstances such as emergencies or for fishing activities.

The pelagic traffic zone is unrestricted and is not available for public use but for general traffic, fishermen and local crafts. A vessel sailing a traffic-lane would navigate the channel throughout the general vicinity. Vessels operating inside the TSS should prevent the waterway among two opposing channels as far as feasible unless under certain situations especially during crisis.

Further improvement of the port can be upheld with profundity which is favorable for development of island and there are potential outcomes to limit the stores for recovery. In addition, the land source inside the region basic to build up the state of port to be widely acclaimed. There is long-shore residue transport restricted and Sungai Linggi dregs transport under controllable circumstance with mellow breezes and waves.

The finding from the respondents likewise shows that, the area is reasonable to huge vessels as there is nearness for profound water notwithstanding that, it is nearby the Malacca Straits Separation Scheme. (TSS).

One of the respondents elaborated further about TSS, which crucial to this part. The IMO-adopted Traffic Separation Scheme (TSS) was established in the SOMS between Permatang Sedepa (One Fathom Bank) and the entrance to the South China Sea in the vicinity of Horsburgh Lighthouse, a total distance of 250 nm. Designated routes for deep-draught vessels and Precautionary Areas are laid down on the charts. Vessels crossing the TSS and Precautionary areas in the Singapore Strait are recommended to display the night signals consisting of 3 all-round green lights in a vertical line. Displaying the night signals shall not exempt the crossing vessel of its obligation to give way to other vessels in a crossing situation or any other rules.

The respondents added that, there has been a proliferation of vessels anchoring within the TSS and Precautionary Areas in the Straits of Malacca and Singapore SOMS as well as between the landward limits of the TSS and approaches to the ports. These vessels pose a risk to the safety of navigation by obstructing traffic flow and port approaches. Mariners are advised of the following concerning anchoring. The location has clear navigation in terms of movement of vessel within the range. KLIP also stays outside of highly-congested choke point of southern part of Malacca Straits. According to Maritime Insights, the Choking point refers to A chokepoint refers to a point of natural congestion along two wider and important navigable passages. Maritime choke points are naturally narrow channels of shipping having high traffic because of their strategic locations.

Since marine choke points were located on crucial marine shipping routes, removing such pinch points has also been proposed as a viable solution in the event of international security issues. Because resisting such maritime shock points in the world will therefore lead to a huge loss in the existence of oil fleet activities, the largest of the CPO freight activities are carried out by navigating through

Interviewees also explained further about the location, where they said the ports is also known as port of refuge as the deep water at anchorage supports the operation of transshipment as it also provides safe area for ships to transfer bunker or cargo in the event of emergency repairs such as breakdown. This is crucial to avoid external cost for instance pollution which can affect the environment. KLIP also equipped with fire-fighting capacity which can assist maritime team in the situation of oil spills and hence alleviate harmful effect to the marine diversity.

There is an offshore facility which encompasses service of fabrication as well as shipyard. KLIP's location is also strategic as it obliged to Malaysia's issue of coastal state by offering assistance to the damaged, disabled or might be in distress in the open sea. The secondary function of KLIP service to provide safer and attractive route to the shipowners and vessel operators. The greatest benefit that can be illustrated as KLIP can complement and benefits all Malaysian ports along the Strait of Malacca cargo transfer area at sea. The operation does not require land facilities as it is fully capitalize the water area near the Linggi.

3. Competition

Based on the secondary data, it is said the port is avoiding competition as they are uniques and only offer limited but premium service by handling liquid materials compare to other conventional ports in Penang, Johor, Klang and Singapore. Most of the interviewees able to describe in detail about ports controlled by MMC, however they mainly focused on Johor and Port Klang which are some of the busiest ports in the world. Some of the also have specific data about the port which able to assist the study. One of the questions posted was "Who are the competitors and how the port is managing rivalry?" The strategic location of KLIP naturally avoid competition but in the west coast there are also several ports along. From

north to south the number are exist and new ports are emerging as well. This is an indication of growth in terms of international trade in Malaysia. The country is experiencing a surplus in balance of payment as weaker RM supports this fact. Foreigners find it cheaper to purchase hence leading to higher export encouraging more transfer of goods and containerization.

4. Customer satisfaction

Interviewees are emphasizing about customer service as they feel that serving clients in any business is the utmost priority which enhances brand value and creates more awareness for publicity. Customers for port will be liners or better known as vessel operators. Excellent service rendered by the port will always have long-term relationship with the clients, where they will become loyal hence comeback over and over again to use the facilities. Having said that, STS is a cost-effective service to crude oil companies such as Shell and Petronas where these businesses able to control their cost structure hence increase profit margin. Petronas being the long-term customer for TAG Marine, this allows popularity can increase as the concept of Natural port can be promoted too.

According to one of the interviewees, he disagrees with the concept of customers satisfaction. He heightened that, focusing on service excellence internally will attract more port calls by the vessel operators. This business is not retail concept as it targets large companies hence maintaining long-term relationship with them is imperative, only by focusing on service excellence. Another respondent also agrees with this concept, as it has to be inward-looking where focusing to improve the service by reducing errors and wastages can create a brand image about the port. It will also allow the port to promote Natural port concept globally as exploitation of resources can be avoided hence increase sustainability. It is also imperative where sustainability can be achieved only by maintain the customers by creating values and solving their problem. One of the ultimate objectives of the port is to reduce cost to the liners and waiting time. This add value to the clients hence allowing KLIP to explore further in this service industry. Under the Linggi Base and TAG Marine flagship the port is planned to enhance its service to large extend.

The main focus will be on reliability, flexibility and safety to the customer. According to the respondents, these elements should gel together in-line with the objective of the business. However, the argument is about ranking of priority of these aspects which dictate sustainably of the business. reliability in service providing – capacity to fulfil what has been promised to the customer, accuracy, precision, and consistency in service providing at first attempt; safety – prevention of possible dangerous situations and risks, financial safety, guaranties.

Flexibility shows the importance to response to the change in demand , whether it is increase or decrease, ensuring service continuous which do not affect the relationship with the customers. Further results from the interview shows importance of customer service which is emphasized by the interviewee can be seen as an important aspect The art of keeping a customer is a strategy of increasing the satisfaction and loyalty. As discussed in the previous chapter, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty are correlated, although the constructs are distinct with one another.

Consumer loyalty is related to as the net end effect and the accumulated relationship consumers have with the brand from the reference point (Brunner, Stöcklin & Opwis 2008). Customer satisfaction contributes to customer loyalty because people have previously had positive experience with the company's products and services. Current customers are much more conscious of and reasonable about managing and mitigating risks up close and personal. In past research, customer satisfaction is deemed to be a sort of service loyalty (Belás & Gabčová 2016; Coelho & Henseler 2012; Lam Shankar, Erramilli & Murthy 2004). Consequently, the connection between such two factors has a favorable result in a successful business organization. As far as customer satisfaction is concerned, customer loyalty in this period is much more essential to firms. Loyal customers are more likely to consume the same organizations' products and services than new ones. On either side, the existing customer serves as a "great marketing force" by sharing ideas, a positive below the line promotion such as word of mouth, behaving as a consultant, and so on (Raman 1999). This will aim to grow the retail industry more efficiently and successfully. In addition, the various kinds of interactions can be discovered between customer loyalty and customer satisfaction, such as satisfaction being the core of loyalty, loyalty being a major part of gratification, satisfaction being the early part of allegiance (Munari, Ielasi & Bjetta 2013). Numerous vectors that boost customer satisfaction described in detail here. "An acceptable outcome is an adequate substitute for good perceived quality, but an exceptional service mechanism develops a distinguishable and appropriate competitive edge" (Grönroos 2007). The degree of the service provided taking into account the demands, identity or environment facets, creates an added value in order to increase

customer loyalty and faithfulness. In order to establish service management, it is important to recognize what clients are just looking for and what they are evaluating. Customer expectations have a resolute effect on the client's viewpoint of the concept of quality. Unforeseen shocks are healthier than great promises in the process of managing quality. Too many promises have destroyed many quality development processes. In the other hand, the management of customer grievances will play a significant role in growing customer service and engagement, as one of the respondents demonstrated.

At a certain point, each organization has to cope with the unfulfilled or frustrated clients. The dilemma is to deal with such customers and to make the customer acknowledge the brand and service provided. Business today requires to exult customers favorably if the organization wants to satisfy the customer and gain loyalty. Apologise profusely and becoming a partner with the customer to eliminate the issues. One of the interviewees also understand about the need for attention on customers but he quoted to Take the opportunity to evaluate the concern with the client and accept the results of being something meaningful (Entrepreneur Organization 2017.) Feedback from customers and data are significant steps in the growth of an entity. Feedback from customers is an important tool for trade associations to enhance their company and brand identity. Feedback is the highest indicator of consumer loyalty. The method of acquiring new business and maintaining current clients can only be done by reviews and consumer grievances. Feedback from consumers offers the concrete evidence to make informed market decisions. Feedback from consumers provides important insight into what customers think of goods and services that help create a profitable business in future. (Client Heartbeat 2015.) Communication and networking infrastructure affects nations around the world (Huang 2015). The delivery of knowledge between staff and consumers lets the business grow. Information networks are an important part of the operating world. New technologies provides new possibilities for business organizations. Data and information infrastructure has led to the exponential development in industry during the last decades. At this time, Internet usage in social media continue to be more than 70%. Social networking is an important medium for consumers to share their interactions with the business and can be seen as a perfect way to increase customer loyalty. Of this reason, the organization will devote greater attention to ensuring that the mechanisms of tracking social networking function effectively. The customer likes to read other consumer comments and suggestions on the grounds that it will be safer for them to make choices on the usage of the liner facility.

According to another finding, In order to acquire the potential customers, needs and demands should be acknowledged also customer satisfaction has a great impact on the entire business operations. Therefore, it is very important to the organization to understand what exactly the customers need and how to gain loyalty for the successful business. As it is discussed in chapter two, the customer plays a crucial role in the market chain process. To make it clearer, satisfied customers are the ones who creates the possibility of the new customers. If the existing customers are satisfied with the product and service, then there are the chances of recommendation to the new ones. This will lead to the increasing number of customers and could maintain the level of the relationship with the customers.

Based on qualitative data, Results in consumer service may also equate different organizations. Comparisons may include a wealth of knowledge either within a department or subgroup or with other agencies. That not only covers institutional and operational capabilities and deficiencies, but also product / service feature functionality and product / service execution. This will help organize proposed improvements unique to each region, as opposed to "blanket" approaches. This may also offer an insight on how one company interacts with another, including its rivalry. This offers the consumer knowledge to make better decisions and selects. 5. Tests in consumer loyalty may help assess management strategies' efficacy. Data obtained from consumer feedback surveys may provide useful, reliable knowledge that can aid in product / service portion assessment and execution. Products / services may be altered to improve performance, and operating procedures can be altered to reach the requirements of quality within a particular sector. In fact, this is the customer-determined norm contrast of a single object. The above-standard scores are good, whereas those below requires enhancement. This makes for more deliberate, planned prioritization of future action measures.

The opinion in terms of this variable which shows the practical way of applying certain strategies to attract clients who are vessel operators. Most importantly efficiency in planning the vessel movement and control which attracts more liners to use the service as this may derive more revenue to KLIP. It is imperative to note that the importance customers satisfaction as building longer-term relationship by having frequent call to the port might reflects good sense of customer orientation. Fundamentally, the aspect of customer service is crucial in any business, however maintain the customer's database through excellent relationship building approach primarily important.

Customer's satisfaction can be the least, as the port is not entertaining retail customers. The port is supported by liner where they transport crude oil and other liquified substances. If the safety regulations followed which doesn't affect the cost then customer's satisfaction can be achieved, hence this variable is weak in the sense of making the implication on the success of the port. The port users who are some locally based and international, such as Maersk, MISC, Bumi Laut, and BP Shipping are generally experts and have experience in this field. Nevertheless, the handling of STS must be carefully done for not losing the clients as this will sustainable growth in term of revenue and profitability.

Despite the benefits of customer satisfaction can be imperative but in shipping, especially in this niche other priorities can more weigh compare to others. According to another participant who has experience in customer service, Customer Experience is the product of how consumers view their client experiences. It is impossible to quantify as the "experience" comprises several elements, from the level of operation to friendliness to consistency in the quality of digital marketing. What the consumers see together and build the consumer experience. That said, a lot of papers were published has been undertaken in recent years to improve customer satisfaction, contributing to consistent and practical measures that can have a beneficial effect on the customer experience of an organization.

Customer Satisfaction (CSAT) is a broad concept reflecting how satisfied consumers are with the company. It is generally achieved through various types of consumer reviews, which are mostly submitted immediately after customer contact. For starters, soon after a consumer reaches support staff, could submit a CSAT survey to determine satisfaction level with the service a business has been provided. (Interviewee 3). Customer satisfaction can be achieved in this context through ad hoc services. KLIP under TAG Marine provides marine facilities and services such Floating storage unit, Distribution, Break bulking & blending, Anchorage for various size of vessel, Lay-up area for various size of vessel on top of STS service.

According to governments' media release, it has signified that the approval is yet given for the operation of the port as it is still pending for cost and benefit analysis. However, it should not interrupt the operation of Port Klang and PTP. According to the report again, it is not allowed to operate container port service as it's close proximity to the other two primary ports in the country serving 23 millions TUEs together.

5. Management Team

One the greatest strengths of KLIP, which is controlled by TAG Marine and Linggi Base would be effectiveness of the management. The company has vibrant managing director YBHG DATUK SERI NOORMUSTAFA KAMAL YAHYA. He plays vital role in formulating corporate strategy for long term growth. This is imperative from the point of view of leader as it consists of element such as identifying goals and achieving them.

Unmistakably, an announcement of what an organization would like to accomplish might be considerably more fluctuated and complex than can be contained in a solitary sentence. This will be particularly valid for those supervisors who are sufficiently complex to see that an organization works in increasingly outside "frameworks" than the market. The firm is part of a market as well as of an industry, the network, the economy, and different frameworks. For each situation there are special connections to watch (e.g., with contenders, metropolitan pioneers, Congress, etc). A progressively complete conversation of this point is contained in a past HBR article.

Based on the outcome of the interview management team under the MD has growth mindset where impressively the plan of the port is futuristic which improves competitiveness of the port operation, attract more liners and ship operators to use the service. The questions asked were What is your role in this company? What are significances of your role towards success of this firm? The information for this question is transparent as it is also available from the secondary sources such as internet and books. However it is important to collect from the respondents themselves as it will give a sense of confidence and direction whether the development of Natural Port integrated port will be feasible or not.

One of the participants recognized the organization's management as process-arranged administration and the interface between sea (business) methodology and sea tasks the executives. The interface between sea system and tasks speaks to the new boondocks of fruition in light of the fact that the business structure and essential markets for request and supply are not differentiable in numerous perspectives. The oceanic business is commanded by a predetermined number of players in each sub-industry, for example, transportation, port administrators and innovation and hardware providers. Basic upper hands may just originate from the successful viewpoint: how an oceanic association or system can maintain their business at low working expense and high assistance quality. Procedure situated research, as a rule, has been seen as a rising

administration worldview, as opposed to the capacity arranged administration worldview (as in the orders offered by business colleges). As sea is fundamentally described as an assistance procedure arranged industry, the business suggest growing new doctoral projects in sea business organization to investigate new research substance, builds, hypotheses and ideal models.

Some of the additional roles of a managing director whom contributes to the success of the origination is the communication skills. Based on the principles of management theory by Mintzberg, communication is imperative to a leader as he or she needs to engage with various stakeholders and ensures messages are disseminated to all the parties at the expected time and accuracy should be maintained.

Pioneers are astounding communicators. The capacity to convey is a center nature of authority. That is on the grounds that 85 percent of your prosperity as a pioneer is controlled by your capacity to discuss adequately with others. All things considered, being a pioneer is tied in with managing others — their prosperity is your prosperity. In the event that you can't convey, you can't be a pioneer. Some of the other roles that are significance to the direction of KLIP will be. According to one of the respondents who is well aware of his role, Direct and control the work and assets of the organization and guarantee the enlistment and maintenance of the necessary numbers and sorts of very much spurred, prepared and created staff to guarantee that it accomplishes its crucial targets.

Set up a corporate arrangement and yearly field-tested strategy and screen progress against these designs to guarantee that the organization achieves its goals as cost-adequately and productively as could reasonably be expected. Offer essential admonition and guidance from the board to the seat and individuals to keep them aware of developments within the company to warrant that appropriate plans are made to reach the strategic destinations of the enterprise and to adhere to any relevant legal and specific guidelines. Creating and retaining effective structured and informal relations with important customers, relevant policy departments and agencies, local experts, community members and different stakeholders, mainly to exchanging data and seeing, and ensuring that the company has the correct context and essence of administrations. Create and retain creative job initiatives to ensure the company is at the center of industry, implements the most financially sophisticated methods and solutions, offers moving edge products and rewards, and retains severe edge.

The participant also emphasized that a leader should Plan, consider, and track the implementation of the annual budget schedule to ensure that budget goals are achieved, revenue sources are improved, and fixed costs are reduced. Establish and retain a successful advertisement and promotional strategy to develop the organization's products, offices, and reputation throughout the broader network. Speak to the company in cooperation with customers, suppliers, policy departments and other primary stakeholders to secure the best conditions for it. Develop and manage Full Quality Management Frameworks in the enterprise to ensure customers provide the finest products and administrations. Create, promote and guide the use of comparable open-door strategies in the organization's function. Track the firm's financial report and documents structure to maintain board approval. Develop and coordinate plans and procedures to ensure that the company meets on both health, protection and other legal standards. However, in order to achieve long term sustaining approach a leader should portray a leadership style of teamwork. this goes contradicted against other respondent as they believe in more dictatorship style. Legitimate is characterized as telling, fearless, and liable to be regarded and complied. Dictator, then again, is characterized as somebody who authorizes severe acquiescence to power, even to the detriment of individual flexibility. To put it plainly, definitive pioneers procure regard, while tyrants request regard.

The leadership reflects how the strategy of an organization is affected in way to influence the stakeholders, mainly internal such as employees , managers and directors. The leadership style approach motivate employees to be more consistent in achieving the level of production and more than that. In the service industry, which is mainly human oriented, high level of interaction is important to have sustainable development and increase in revenue. It is widely acceptable that, the democratic leadership style is the most practical one when it comes to managing a business as it requires two communication from bottom to the top, hence to certain extend it is a decentralized approach.

Another specialized role in the company will be marine advisor. One of the important responsibilities of the advisors will be providing strategic advice in terms of operation of subsea cons dividing, subsea construction, supply operations, survey vessels, towing, anchor handling, heavy lift, geotechnical sampling, pipe laying, rock dumping and other special vessels. Rig moving of jackups and semisubmersibles, including detailed anchor plans.

According to participant, based on outcome of the interview. In addition to this the relevant respondent supported the research by specifically addressing some roles, such as

- Vessel inspections and suitability evaluations of vessels and construction barges
- Rig Tendering and negotiation
- Contract Management for rigs and various service companies.
- Maintain Marine Control Procedure and define requirements for marine operations
- Focal point and coordinator for marine operations
- Prepare, co-ordinate and execute audits and inspections on board the accommodation rig(s)
- Ensure that all rig moves within DUC are conducted in a safe and efficient manner.
- Host rig move meetings.
- Conduct risk assessments for rig moves.
- Implementing Incident free mind set in contractors and subcontractors
- HSEQ Reporting in accordance with company requirements
- Rig supervision and management of accommodation rigs
- Marine/Client representative on board rigs and vessels

According to him again, his role is highly specialized and requires someone who is experienced to perform the task. The specialization adds value to the concept of STS which further reducing cost of operation and increase the profit margin.

The position often includes a professional with a maritime experience, coupled with mechanical aptitude. Guided and continue to demonstrate effort. The job holder always be rational, organized and consistent, coupled with imaginative thought. Someone employed at sea and wish to try a new onshore role, this job will raise obstacles that sea expertise can support by conducting Marine Management Community practices to progress to the next phase of the career. Moreover, strong interaction and communication skills are necessary and high activity encouragement, combined with the competency to alleviate ad hoc challenges on regular basis. A specific guidance system would be available on the position if necessary. The job is onshore focused and the function would entail minimal offshore visits and/or transport.

However, based on qualitative finding there is conflict at strategic level decision making process as some roles within the organization clash each other in terms of job specification. The decision in terms marine operation involves advisor to give inputs to the Managing Direction where it requires careful considerations.

At some points it leads to conflicts between individuals in top management which tends to delay important decision-making process, especially when it comes to responding to the changes in the macro environment. Primary aspect will be about changes in regulations, competition and managing customers, which requires instant decision to be made. However, delayed response can be catastrophic where most importantly it affects the revenue of the firm.

Some of the considerations when it comes to leadership is about trust building. According to one of the interviewees, it is imperative to explore the importance of trust as a core belief and feeling that can develop between leaders and followers. Because trust is a relational concept that occurs between people, both leaders and followers play a critical role in creating, sustaining, destroying, and rebuilding trusting relationships. The chapter is structured as follows: the business will first consider the role of trust in the leadership relationship, emphasizing that trust is a critical foundation for both effective exchange-based and motivational leader-follower relationships. The business will then explore the antecedents and consequences of trust in leader-follower relations, exploring what factors predict when trust is more or less likely to develop, as well as the different outcomes that often result from trusting versus mistrusting relationships. In addition, the business will consider situations where trust can act as an important buffer against negative workplace experiences. Finally, the business will explore when and why leaders are more likely to trust their followers, the dynamic transfer of trust between leaders and followers, and mistrust and trust repair.

Other than that, effective management also emphasizes on problem solving and importance given to the stakeholders when it comes to decision making. Chief Executive Officer or simply CEO carries vital roles to support the managing director. There are arguments in terms of jurisdiction of a CEO and MD, however generally, MD leads the BOD while CEO leads the management team for strategic decision who is responsible to supervise deputies, presidents or vice presidents.

The root of leader-follower confidence, nevertheless, may still be linked to these two basic components: how leaders determine that they have the capacity to lead efficiently, demonstrating mission and conversation-oriented abilities, and how they develop their generosity and honesty. Furthermore, the figureheads have two main structures to build these pillars. The response-based paradigm argues that positive, participatory, and encouraging management activities convey a message that the individual has trust and interest in his or her followers and that such leadership activities in turn promote higher rates of leadership faith. Many management ideas emphasize a similar trust-building process, which suggests more chances to engage in policy-making within the organisation offer members more benefits from performing their job and help them become more motivated. The consequence is enhanced confidence in the leader.

The important role of confidence in effective leadership has long been understood. Bass's transition management concept concluded that this leader-ship style is partially successful by promoting follower confidence. Some work shows that the connection between transformational management and success relies on the leadership and interest congruence of both followers. For example, in a research & development team report, engaging team members while taking choices, expressing a mutual mission, and discussing shared beliefs with the leader projected 67% of employee confidence scores in their leaders. Such leadership actions combined show that the top people in the organisation is unlikely to breach faith, encouraging followers to exchange confidential details and focus on leader decisions in uncertain circumstances.

Equally, faith is a central legal, worker, and trustworthy types of leadership. Work confirms the vital position that supporters play in their manager's views of honesty and confidence, which in effect affects followers' attitudes and results. Increasingly, information employees need an accountable leader whose principles resonate with the company's goal to lead with honesty and confidence. leadership style of authentic is inherently trust-based, fostering a more open and straightforward method while coping with tough issues. A trustworthy leader will first build "credits" with prospective supporters before willing to be guided in a new direction; as a result, more honest and optimistic leaders are more likely to have supporters who support them and regard them as successful leaders.

A performance emerges through effective, trust-building management. Staff can be strongly encouraged with confidence that makes freedom to a degree. This is important to consider workers' desire that it can be fulfilled through inspiring them through successful leadership method. Adding further, one respondent emphasizes the degree of legitimacy it may create among internal stakeholders. Another respondent paid more attention in terms of functions of a CEO and how it can strategically affect implementation and promotion of a Natural Port. According to him the roles of CEO based on the interviewee is :

Authority · The CEO works under the authority granted by the Board according to the guidelines set out below and as may be given from time to time. · Approval by the Board (or relevant body) shall be needed for any important actions beyond the usual course of operation of the Company, including substantial funding, investments, regulations, expenditures and capital investment as set out in the Corporation's policies and procedures.

The CEO has the greatest personal and has intellectual credibility. The CEO shall behave sincerely and in good conscience toward the Corporation's interests and practice the consideration, caution and ability that a fairly responsible individual might possess in comparable circumstances. · The CEO prevents future or current improprieties with the Company or any concerns inconsistent with the CEO's role. CEO must conform with the Corporation's existing regulations, encompassing the Compliance Policy and Corporate Practices and Ethics Law, and the board's jurisdiction limits. The CEO is solely responsible for handling the activities of the Company, working in the best interests of the Organization and its securityholders. The CEO shall be entirely accountable for the Organization's activities in compliance with the financial strategy and current year operational and capital spending expenditures as authorized by the Management board. Connection with the board of directors · Interacts periodically and when necessary with the board chair and other board members to ensure that all data is given in a reasonable time manner and has accessibility to administration to allow the board to satisfy its regulatory and other obligations. Being mindful of the Firm's success and any activities impacting its company is another

imperative characteristic of a CEO, in this case TAG Marine and Linggi Base including market trends and positive or negative developments.

Leadership · Create a safe, professional workplace atmosphere that recruits, maintains and motivates top-quality workers at all levels. · Partner with key leaders to foster a workplace ethical company climate and develop expectations and governance mechanisms that are adequately structured to uphold transparency and discourage misconduct. · Constantly encourage chief managers and workers to act creatively. · Ensure that all Company workers have specifically specified roles and authority. · Cultivate a business community that encourages responsible standards and fosters honesty and corporate accountability.

Strategic Planning · Build, for Board review at least quarterly, a strategic strategy detailing the course and strategies to achieve sustainable development and progress. Set strategic goals and accepted long-term plans, protocols and organizational objectives which gives as sense of direction while create a policy structure for monetary and human capital distribution.

Financial preparation Create comprehensive realistic operating strategies and priorities for the Board to achieve the Corporation's targets and objectives. Coordinate and control the Corporation's operations to ensure that strategic, financial, and operating goals are achieved and the Corporation's properties are protected and managed in the best interests of the Company and its protection owners. Define, to the degree practicable, all major threats to the Company's operations and evaluate and develop policies to minimize the effects of the threats. · Track pay, performance evaluation, teamwork, career growth and management succession planning. 3 **Contact and Relationships.** Offer monthly and yearly certification covering financial report performance and related review and examination by management. **Succession Planning** by building and implement a strategic strategy to improve and handle senior executives' success, including recruitment, preparation, mentoring and supervision of these officers. Renew the Company's obligation to provide prompt, correct and fair disclosure of all relevant facts on the Business in compliance with the Reporting Policy and applicable securities laws. Establish and execute organizational policy to guide the Organization under the limitations imposed by relevant laws and regulations and a plan process authorized by the Board. Identify strategic safety guidelines, set efficiency goals for running companies and maintain commitment to policies and standards. Develop, track and sustain adequate management processes for successful central organizational control which deemed to more vital when it comes developing a Natural Port. Develop constructive partnerships with creditors and other key stakeholders, including states, the financial industry and the media. Find and grow possible replacements that may occupy CEO and other important senior executive roles now or in the future. The Organizational Control and Appointment Committee and the Board of Directors evaluate these guidelines periodically.

A rise in management salary usually has business shareholders' attention. Improvements occur at the cost of company gains, while most recognize that fair compensation helps attract industry talent. The board of trustees, though, agrees to raise employee compensation. According to the respondent, in the event where CEO is also the chairperson, a conflict of interest emerges as the CEO votes on his own compensation. Because a board is mandated by statute to include certain representatives outside of administration, the chair may control the board's actions, which causes the leadership position manipulated.

The interview regarding the role of the director of marine and head are playing vital part in making the concept of STS and Natural Port become more practical. The Director of Marine Operations must appreciate and support the Institute's mission and vision, while challenging the Institute to improve its operating effectiveness and efficiency. The role holder will recognize and build new concepts and resources and promote progress in a collaborative governance climate. A strategic visionary with strong leadership skills and demonstrated ability to effectively foster a comparable performance culture, customer care, transparency, and dignity. The effective leader must also exhibit poise and personality with outstanding communication abilities and a clear market acumen to manage corporate systems and efficiencies and build trust to establish good partnerships with a range of voters and stakeholders. The Director of Marine Operations (DMO) accounts to the Chief Operations Officer (COO) for supervision, strategic preparation, management and review of the Institute's vessel activities, servicing, restoration, construction, maritime health and underwater services. Although the COO may offer general advice in operational issues, the DMO may maintain extensive technological and organizational expertise when being accountable for all facets of vessel activities and must regularly make substantive judgments in situations that no one else in the Institution is eligible offer advice. The role also offers guidance in policies and practices for ship activities and maintaining optimal health, preparation, performance and efficacy through the usage of capital to meet the Institute's priorities and aims.

The Director of Marine Operations controls and operates all aspects of the Institution's maritime activity organisation, covering monetary administration, personnel control, organizational development, health & educational activities, and ship repair.

The other participants have gathered in addition to their opinions. Manages the Maritime Operations' diverse processes and practices Sets the overall course and assures the organization's progress by guiding the production of priorities and strategies that are compatible with and promote the Institute's operational purpose. · Guarantees that the Institution's vessel fleet performs in compliance with the best practicable health requirements and acceptable U.S. Coast Patrol, Loadline and Vessel Ship Identification at all stages. · Conduct efficient preventive maintenance, establish a target framework for delayed repair jobs, and enforce inspection systems. · Guarantees proper control and utilization of Institutes tools, including the production and maintenance of all aquatic budgets. · Assists in securing international support for R / V Virginia by selling the vessel in relevant journals and support channels.

The hierarchy of TAG Marines shows some layers are not really effective as incur cost of paying additional higher levels staff, this is critical in identifying redundancy in the operation. Increase in demand might need more attention in layers as more man power needed for this which makes a business to be successful.

According to a participant , the advisory role may be not needed as the director and head play significant role in identifying the daily operational need for the business. The role of advisor merely remains for pre-planning purpose hence when it comes to implementation of this function is becoming limited. It doesn't show any key to the success. However in some occasion advisory role is more visible, especially during crisis management.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This part concludes the research and offers recommendation to TAG Marine and LBSS on the important factors that should be considered when it comes to development of the Natural Port as well as STS concept of transferring liquid. Total of 5 respondents were chosen using non- probability sampling method as they were asked with set of qualitative questions form the category of 7 independent variables. The decision and recommendation will be based on the feedback received from the respondents which will be supported by secondary data.

One of the most independent variables is highly influential and make the Natural port to be successful is the management team. The top executives and directors are well aware of their duties and extremely knowledge where they will be able to develop the port to a greater success. From Managing Director to Marine Head, all of the are highly competent as they valuable experience to handle the situation well.

Building and promoting a port requires huge sum and it takes longer time to break even, however with combination of right skills and concentration in human capital allow TAG Marine and LBSS to successfully implement the new venture. The individual in the organisation are well aware of the task and challenge they might as they work as a team to support each and encourage young talent to join the industry and grow together. In addition to this, the team is clear in terms objective that should be achieved.

Another most encouraging variable will be the strategic location. The venture will be highly profitable as many oil producing countries able to use the service to transfer the crude oil. Malacca strait can be a hub for oil producing countries from west where they want to deliver the liquid to eastern countries. This will be shortening the transfer time; the vessel will avoid berthing time as well as other charges that might incur when she uses conventional port. Adding more on this, according to one of the respondents, the Linggi port currently serves 400 clients worldwide hence potential to grow will be very high.

However this justification is made based on the cater paribus concept as other external factors such as , politics, economy, environment , legal , technology and social remain status quo. In 2017, combined oil production of USA, Saudi Arabia and Russia exceeded more 1.5 billion tonnes of volume of oil. Oil is an inelastic good, hence despite increase in price consumer and firms must use in daily operation. Growth of export of oil is phenomenon as it can be anticipated more tankers will be arriving in the coast of Malacca.

The Natural location of the port where it is away from competition gives competitive edge to the company. Besides that, selection of services which are not offered in other ports as well as core service of ship-to-ship transfer for liquid-based goods, makes Port of Linggi be distinctive among others. Recent news from Indonesia where they hired tankers form a floating storage offered by TAG Marine supports the plan that the Natural Port will become a success.

The most least effect is the variable of customer satisfaction. Most of the respondents are aware of the importance of customer's loyalty but the feasibility in term of ship operation remain questionable. If the port offers container shipment service then it can be concluded that customers service is high important, however TAG Marine is servicing industrial clients hence the customer satisfaction will be least important compare to the service deliver. In this case the service delivery means the business itself. Some respondents agree that, if good service given to the calling vessels and fulfil requirement it is in a way achieving the certain level of customer satisfaction, in this case will be the vessel/tanker operators

In conclusion, the research findings highlight the significant impact of cryptocurrencies on international trade and economic relationships. Cryptocurrencies have the potential to streamline cross-border transactions, transform economic relationships, and promote financial inclusion. However, challenges related to regulation, volatility, and cybersecurity need to be addressed to fully harness the benefits of cryptocurrencies in international trade. The policy implications and recommendations outlined in this research provide a roadmap for policymakers to navigate the evolving landscape of cryptocurrencies and maximize their potential in transforming global trade.

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